

StandICT.eu2029

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

Standardisation Meetings (SM) Open Calls main guidelines

June 2026

Funded by
the European Union

Introduction

This document provides the main guidelines for applicants who are interested in applying for **StandICT.eu 2029 Open Calls**, in particular the application for Organisation of Standardisation Meetings.

The objective of the funding is to enable applicants to contribute to and help create a fully integrated European Standardisation Ecosystem, thereby strengthening Europe's position in global standardisation initiatives.

Description of SM contribution

The Organisation of Standardisation Meetings (SM) is introduced under this edition, aimed at supporting the hosting of international standardisation meetings in Europe in European Associated Countries. In this particular funding typology, the maximum funding per application is set at 50.000€, and the same organisation may only be awarded once under this scheme for the duration of the project.

The maximum duration of the fellowship is set for 6 months depending on the scale and timing of the meeting.

A total budget of approximately 200.000€ will be allocated via this open call.

Process and timing for Open Call for Applications

StandICT.eu 2029 will run a continuous Open Call (with no set deadline) for proposal submission. The call will stay open until all the available budget has been allocated.

All proposals received through TRUST-GRANTS™ platform will be screened for eligibility, evaluated by an external pool of evaluators (EPE), scored, and ranked for funding.

The evaluation is done in bulk as soon as a sufficient number of applications is received. The applicants submitting their application in June 2026, July 2026 or August 2026 may expect feedback during the month of September 2026.

Applicants submitting at a later stage, should funding still be available will receive information about the expected timeline for evaluation in a revised version of these guidelines

All applicants shall be notified with the result of the evaluation process (e.g., retained fellowships or not successful application) and provided with access to a Consensus Report compiled by the evaluators part of the StandICT.eu 2029 External Pool of Evaluators (EPE).

To guarantee maximum fairness and transparency, each application will be independently evaluated by two members of the EPE and will undergo Quality Control by the StandICT.eu consortium and the EC (European Commission) after consensus is reached.

As the EPE are highly-skilled experts whose qualifications are assessed through an open call process their decision is binding and any redress requests or complaints will be dealt with strictly in relation to the procedural aspects of the evaluation and not on the merits of scientific or technical judgement of the experts.

Possible outcomes of the evaluation

At the end of the evaluation process, applicants will be officially notified of one of the following outcomes:

Funded

The proposal has been successfully evaluated and approved exactly as submitted. The application fully meets all criteria, requires no further modifications, and will be awarded the requested funding, provided that all the necessary reporting documents and invoices are submitted on time.

Funded with Modifications Requested

The proposal is valuable and has been selected for funding, contingent upon the implementation of specific adjustments requested by the Evaluation Committee. In some cases, these modifications are mandatory and must be applied exactly as requested. In other instances, a mutual agreement can be negotiated to find a feasible solution.

Waiting List

The proposal successfully meets the evaluation criteria but cannot be funded immediately due to budget limitations. Applications placed on this list may be elevated to "Funded" or "Funded with Modifications Requested" status if higher-ranked applicants decline their grant, fail to reach an agreement regarding requested modifications, or ultimately become unable to organise their event.

Not funded

The proposal has not been selected for funding. This outcome occurs if the application does not meet the minimum required evaluation thresholds or if the available budget has been exhausted by higher-scoring proposals.

Criteria for receiving financial support (Eligibility)

- The target applicants are organisations based in a European Member State or Associated Country, but located in EU with a demonstrable role in coordinating or supporting the organisation of meetings on behalf of international SDOs, global fora, or consortia.
- The proposed meetings must align with the thematic scope defined in the application form, i.e. refer to one or more of the central Policy Areas of the ICT Rolling Plan
- While co-funding from other sources is permitted, the activities supported by StandICT.eu 2029 must be clearly identified and not double-funded.
- The funding exclusively covers the technical meetings; therefore, it will not finance a larger conference that includes this meeting.
- The same organisation can only be awarded once, hence applying for a continuation of the previously funded activities is not permitted in this case. If an application is not funded, re-application which addresses the gaps of the previous application is permitted

The most recent information listing participating countries in Horizon Europe issued by the Commission at the time of writing (25/07/2023) can be consulted here [EU Grants: List of participating countries \(HE\) V2.9 – 21.03.2025](#). Please refer to this document if you have any doubts as to your eligibility for funding.

Criteria for evaluation

The initial eligibility screening will be undertaken by the Consortium to assess compliance to the call. Proposals which are ineligible for any reason or which do not meet the call criteria will be identified as such, and the applicant will receive a notification from the team. The consortium will consolidate all eligible proposals and submit them to the external evaluators (selected from the External Pool of Evaluators – EPE) to undertake the formal evaluation.

Each proposal will be evaluated on the basis of the following four criteria principle:

- **Criterion 1** – Strategic Objective and Agenda (Weight: 20%) – Focus: Assessment of objective relevance, EC priority alignment, and agenda coherence.
- **Criterion 2** – Expected Outcome and Impact (Weight: 35%) – Focus: Assessment of deliverable feasibility, impact validity, and the strategic value of StandICT.eu involvement and European focus.
- **Criterion 3** – Implementation, Team & Budget Justification (Weight: 30%) – Focus: Assessment of team expertise, operational planning, and budget justification for value for money.
- **Criterion 4** – Inclusiveness & Balance (Weight: 15%) – Focus: Assessment of proactive measures for organizational diversity, SME inclusion, demographic balance, and geographic spread.

Scores will range from 1 to 10. The final scoring and ranking will be automatically determined by averaging the scores provided by the two independent members of the External Pool of Evaluators after a consensus.

To ensure a diverse and balanced portfolio of funded fellowship, the evaluation process will pay attention to organisational diversity. During the final selection phase, the committee will ensure that the awarded proposals represent a wide variety of organisations affiliated with a wide range of different Standard Developing Organisations (SDOs).

Financial aspects

The grant is not released as a single lump sum; rather, it is divided into an initial pre-payment upon award and a final balance paid after the event. To release the final payment, the submission of a comprehensive report detailing all meeting outcomes, receipts and invoices is required to ensure accountability and verify the results.

The maximum funding available to each funded applicant under this grant scheme is €50,000. Applicants must ensure that their proposed total of reimbursable costs remains entirely within this maximum limit, as expenses exceeding this amount will not be covered.

Please note that all post-event documentation, including the comprehensive outcome report and the final invoices, must be formally submitted no later than 31 August 2028. This strict deadline is mandatory to ensure our financial department can process and complete all final payments by 15 September 2028. Consequently, if there are any delays in submitting the required reporting or invoices past the August 31 deadline, we cannot guarantee the execution of the final payment. Any submissions received after this timeframe risk being completely ineligible for reimbursement due to the definitive financial closure of StandICT.eu 2029 on 30 September 2028.

How to apply

Applicants who already applied for StandICT.eu 2029, 2026 and 2023 Open Calls can log in with the old credentials.

New applicants will have to first create a new account, and then once registered they can access the application form.

Applicants must then fill in the application form with the required information.

The application can also be saved into draft and modified anytime until the closing date of the open call. Please remember to officially submit your application by clicking the 'Submit' button.

Please note that once submitted, no further modifications will be possible.

To access your saved draft later, simply log in using your previously created account.

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If you have
any questions
please contact us

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General questions: info@standict.eu

Once your proposal is successfully awarded,
you may reach out for support to:

Mona Marill, Manager of awarded grants
mona@australo.org

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